

Supporting Information

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Orthogonal Light-Dependent Membrane Adhesion
Induces Social Self-Sorting and Member-Specific DNA
Communication in Synthetic Cell Communities

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Materials and Methods

1-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)-3-ethylcarbodiimide HCl (Sigma 98%), 2-Ethyl-1-hexanol (Sigma, 98%), 1,6-diaminohexane (Sigma, 98%), Rhodamine B isothiocyanate (RBITC, 70%, Sigma), PEG-bis(N-succinimidyl succinate) (MW=2000, Sigma), streptavidin from *Streptomyces avidinii* (Sigma), Atto425-Biotin (Sigma 95%), bovine serum albumin (heat shock fraction, pH=7.0, $\geq 98\%$, Sigma), Acryloyl chloride ($\geq 97\%$, Sigma), N_{α},N_{α} -Bis(carboxymethyl)-L-lysine hydrate ($\geq 97\%$, Sigma), Dowex resin 50WX8 (Sigma). All DNA oligonucleotides were purchased from Integrated DNA Technologies with HPLC purification, dissolved in 10 mM Tris (pH=8.0) and stored at -20°C . All other reagents were purchased from Sigma Aldrich.

^1H and ^{13}C spectra were recorded on a Varian 400 MHz spectrometer. ^1H NMR spectra are reported as δ in units of parts per million (ppm) relative to water or methanol (δ 4.65, s; δ 4.87, s respectively). The number of protons (n) for a given resonance is indicated as $n\text{H}$, and was based on spectral integration values. ^{13}C NMR spectra are reported as δ in units of parts per million (ppm) relative to CDCl_3 (δ 77.23, t).

UV-Vis spectroscopy experiments were performed using a PerkinElmer Lambda750 spectrophotometer using plastic cuvettes. Blanks were automatically subtracted from each spectrum.

Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectra were recorded using a Perkin Elmer Spectrum One spectrophotometer equipped with an attenuated total reflectance sampling accessory. Polymer and protein-polymer conjugate samples were measured directly as solids, and the blank was automatically subtracted from each spectrum.

DLS and zeta-potential measurements were performed on a ZETASIZER Nano series instrument (Malvern Instruments, UK) using 1 mg/mL solutions of proteins or protein-polymer conjugates at pH 7.0 (10 mM PBS buffer).

Matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time of flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF MS) was performed on a 4700 Proteomics analyzer (Applied Biosystems). The preparation of BSA, BSA/PNIPAM-co-NTA and PNIPAM-co-NTA samples required three solutions; (1) 3 equivalents of DHAP in EtOH (20.3 mg/mL) and 1 equivalent DAHC in water (18 mg/mL), (2) 2 vol% TFA

in water, and (3) 2-3 mg/mL of protein, polymer or protein-polymer conjugate in water. The three solutions were mixed in 1:1:1 volume ratio and spotted on the MALDI plate.

For all the experiments, red light (Albrillo LL-GL003, 225 LEDs, 660 nm, 14 W, 544 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$) LED light panel, and blue light (Albrillo LL-GL003, 225 LEDs, 480 nm, 14 W, 544 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$) were used.

Expression and purification of proteins

The plasmids pQE-80L iLID (C530M) and pQE-80L MBP-SspB Nano were gifts from Brian Kuhlman (Addgene # 60408 and 60409, respectively)^[1]. The N-terminal His6-tagged iLID and Nano proteins were expressed and purified as previously reported.^[2] PhyB protein was encoded in the plasmid pMH1105 (a gift from Dr. Maximilian Hörner and Prof. Wilfried Weber) was expressed and purified through its His-tag following the reported protocol.^[3] The PIF6-GFP-His6-tag in pET21b vector was expressed and purified as previously described.^[4] His-GFP (N-terminally His6-tagged, Addgene # 29663) was recombinantly expressed in *E. coli* and purified over a Ni^{2+} -NTA column using standard protocols. The purity of the proteins was verified using SDS-PAGE and the protein concentrations were determined by UV-vis spectroscopy.

Synthesis of 2,20-(5-acrylamido-1-carboxypentylazanediy)diacetic acid (NTA-acrylate) (1)

The synthesis was carried out using a modified version of the procedure of M. Ehrbar and co-workers.^[5] N_{α},N_{α} -Bis(carboxymethyl)-L-lysine hydrate (0.7868 mg, 3 mmol) was dissolved in 27 mL of 0.44 M NaOH and the solution was cooled to 0 °C. Acryloyl chloride (0.322 mL, 4.0 mmol) was dissolved in 15 mL of dry toluene and added dropwise to the cold solution of N_{α},N_{α} -Bis(carboxymethyl)-L-lysine. The biphasic solution was vigorously stirred overnight at room temperature. The morning after the reaction mixture was transferred into a separatory funnel, and the toluene layer discarded. The aqueous layer was then washed two more times with toluene to remove the excess acryloyl chloride. The aqueous layer was then distilled down to a few mL, transferred into a 50 mL plastic test-tube, and diluted to 30 mL with MilliQ water. To this solution 10 mL of Dowex 50WX8 resin were added and the solution was gently shaken for 30 min. The resin was then removed through gooch filtration on a bed of sand and washed with MilliQ water until the pH of washes was neutral. The resulting clear aqueous solution containing the product was concentrated down to a few mL and lyophilised.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, D₂O): δ 6.11 (dd, $J_a = 16$ Hz, $J_b = 8$ Hz, 1H), 6.01 (d, $J = 16$ Hz, 1H), 5.59 (d, $J = 16$ Hz, 1H), 4.00 (s, 4H), 3.96 (dd, $J_a = 12$ Hz, $J_b = 4$ Hz 1H), 3.14 (t, $J_a = 8$ Hz, 2H), 1.91-1.74 (m, 2H), 1.52-1.32 (m, 4H). ¹³C NMR (128 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 170.4, 169.0, 168.3, 130.0, 127.0, 66.9, 54.1, 38.6, 27.7, 26.4, 22.7. HRMS (m/z): calcd. for C₁₃H₂₁N₂O₇ [M+H]⁺, 317.1343; found, 317.1329.

Synthesis of mercaptothiazoline-activated PNIPAM-co-NTA (2)

N-isopropylacrylamide and AIBN were freshly recrystallized from hexane and methanol, respectively. Mercaptothiazoline-activated RAFT agent was synthesised according to our

previously established procedure.^[6] *N*-isopropylacrylamide (0.450 g; 3.98 mmol), NTA-acrylate (50 mg, 0.16 mmol; 4 mol%, 10 wt%), and AIBN (30 mg, 0.18 mmol) were dissolved in 3 mL of methanol, and added to a small round bottom flask equipped with a stirrer bar. To this solution mercaptothiazoline-activated RAFT agent (12.8 mg, 34.5 μmol) dissolved in 1 mL of acetonitrile was added. The solution was purged with argon for 30 min and the flask sealed. Polymerization was carried out at 65 °C for 8 h with stirring at 700 rpm. The polymer was isolated by precipitation from 1:1 hexane/Et₂O (250 mL) as a crystalline light-yellow powder in 96 wt% yield. M_n 5760 g mol⁻¹, M_w 5800 g mol⁻¹, PDI 1.01, 5 mol% in NTA-acrylate. See Supplementary figure 2 for ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra. From the integration reported in Supplementary figure 2 and molecular weight of the polymer it is possible to calculate that in average the polymeric chains are composed by 44 NIPAM units and 3 NTA units.

The LCST was estimated through UV-Vis turbidity measurements, and by acquiring the transmittance between 550 and 600 nm of a 1 mg mL⁻¹ polymer solution in MilliQ water. Data points were acquired at different temperatures from 25 to 45 °C, and 5 min of equilibration time was waited between the spectrum acquisitions. The experiment was repeated in triplicate. The cloud point temperature (T_{cp}), taken as the 50% of the initial transmittance value, was determined to 34 °C, see figure S9.

Preparation of BSA/PNIPAM-co-NTA conjugates

Labelling of BSA with fluorescent dyes: In general, 20.9 mg of BSA were dissolved in 7.74 mL of Na₂CO₃ buffer (pH 8.5, 100 mM), and 193.5 μL of a DMSO solution of a Rhod B isothiocyanide dye (1.0 mg/mL) added. The conjugation reaction was performed for 5 h at room temperature. The Rhod B-conjugated BSA was purified by dialysis using 12-14 kDa MWCO membranes, lyophilized and stored as a solid at -20 °C.

Cationization of BSA: In a vial, 18 mg of unlabelled or RhodB-labelled BSA were dissolved in 1.8 mL of water. In a separate vial, 180 mg of hexamethylenediamine were dissolved in 1.8 mL of water and the pH was adjusted to 6.0. The hexamethylenediamine solution was slowly added to the BSA solution under vigorous stirring, and the pH readjusted to 6.0. The cationization reaction was initiated by adding 9.0 mg of EDAC dissolved in 500 μL of water. After 2 h, another 9 mg of EDAC dissolved in 500 μL of water were added. The reaction was left under stirring at room temperature for 18 h. BSA-NH₂ was purified by dialysis, centrifuged (5 min, 5000 rpm) to remove any precipitate, and then lyophilised and stored as a solid at -20 °C. On average, this procedure resulted in a 30 % level of cationization as determined by MALDI-TOF spectrometry.

BSA/PNIPAM-co-NTA: In a vial, 20 mg of unlabelled or RBITC-labelled cationized BSA were dissolved in 10 mL of Na₂CO₃ buffer (pH 8.5, 100 mM). In a separate vial, 20 mg of mercaptothiazoline-activated PNIPAM-co-NTA were dissolved in 10 mL of water. The mercaptothiazoline-activated PNIPAM-co-NTA solution was added dropwise to a stirred solution of cationized BSA, and the conjugation reaction carried out for 18 h at room temperature. BSA/PNIPAM-co-NTA conjugate was then isolated by centrifugation using centrifugal filters

with 50 kDa MWCO. The residues were washed 4 times to remove any unreacted polymer, and the product lyophilised and stored as a solid at -20 °C.

Preparation of the streptavidin-containing Ni²⁺-NTA proteinosomes

7.5 µL of BSA/PNIPAM-co-NTA conjugates (final concentration: 16 mg/ml) and 4.2 µL streptavidin (final concentration: 10 µM) dissolved in buffer (50 mM sodium carbonate pH 8.5) were mixed in an Eppendorf tube and 1.5 mg of PEG-bis (*N*-succinimidyl succinate) (M_w = 2000, Sigma) dissolved in 3.3 µL buffer was added to the mixture. Afterwards, a Pickering emulsion was produced by adding 600 µL of 2-ethyl-1-hexanol and vortexing for 25 s. The sample was kept for at least 3 h at room temperature in the dark for the crosslinking reaction to take place. The upper oil layer was removed and then, the emulsion was dispersed into 400 µL of 70% ethanol and dialyzed sequentially in 70% ethanol (2 h), 50% ethanol (4 h) and water (overnight). The proteinosomes suspension was stored at 4 °C. For the loading of the NTA groups with Ni²⁺ ions, were the resulting proteinosomes in water dialyzed against 10 mM NiCl₂ for 3 h, at 4 °C. The excess NiCl₂ was dialyzed away against water overnight at 4 °C.

10 µL of the FITC-labeled streptavidin solutions with 3.5 µM, 7.5 µM, and 15 µM concentrations were fixed between the coverslips. The intensity values were measured using the same settings on the confocal microscope as for the proteinosomes. The streptavidin concentration in the proteinosomes was fitted to the calibration curve.

Localization of DNA complexes in streptavidin-containing proteinosomes

Following the previously published protocols,^[7,8] the DNA gate complexes were loaded into proteinosomes in 10 mM Tris Buffer pH 8.0 with 12 mM Mg²⁺ and 0.1% v/v Tween 20. Typically, a dispersion of streptavidin-containing proteinosomes (10 µL), and 2 µL of biotinylated F strands (final concentration 1.2 µM) were gently mixed and incubated at room temperature for 1 h. Then 2 µL of the corresponding quencher strands Q (final concentration: 1.6 µM) was added to the mixture and incubated at 4°C overnight. Subsequently, for labeling the R2 proteinosomes, 5 µL of 500 nM Atto425-biotin solution was added to 10 µL of receiver proteinosomes and incubated for 10-15 min at room temperature. To remove the excess strands, 10 µL of the supernatant was removed carefully from the top and 10 µL buffer was added. Proteinosomes were allowed to sediment for 7 h at 4°C and 10 µL supernatant from the top was removed and 400 µL buffer were added. The proteinosomes suspension was allowed to sediment for 7-8 h and the top 380 µL of buffer were removed. The resulting DNA gate loaded proteinosomes were stored at 4°C.

Protein immobilization on the proteinosomes

In the dark, 1 µL BSA (stock concentration 2 mg/mL) was added to 10 µL of Ni²⁺-NTA/PNIPAM proteinosomes (loaded with DNA gate complexes beforehand where necessary) and incubated for 5 min at room temperature. Then, 2 µL of His-tagged protein (total final concentration 500 nM) were added to the mixture and the sample was incubated room temperature for 10-20 min. iLID

and PhyB proteins were added in equal portions at the same time for the functionalization of the S proteinosome and PIF6 and Nano were added to R1 and R2 proteinosomes, respectively.

Surface density of proteins on the proteinosomes

Following the previously reported protocol,^[9] the surface density of proteins on proteinosomes was quantified by functionalizing the proteinosomes with different concentration of His6-tagged GFP (His6-GFP) and comparing the fluorescent signal of the membrane bound protein on the proteinosomes with GUV membrane prepared with 1 mol% DGS-NTA. The average fluorescence intensity along the vesicle contour was measured using the (Radial Profile Extended plugin, Philippe Carl). The fluorescent background level was estimated from micrographs where DGS-NTA or PNIPAM-co-NTA were absent for GUVs and proteinosomes, respectively. Finally, by taking the area per lipid a conversion factor was obtained, which was then used to convert membrane fluorescent intensities to GFP surface coverage on proteinosomes.

The experimental data are well fitted by the linear relationship $\Gamma = (67 \pm 2) \times \mu\text{m}^{-2} \text{ nM}^{-1}$ for GUVs and $\Gamma = (109 \pm 8) \times \mu\text{m}^{-2} \text{ nM}^{-1}$ for proteinosomes over the concentration range of $0 < X \leq 23 \text{ nM}$. Consequently, the GFP concentration $X = 500 \text{ nM}$ leads to the coverage of $\Gamma = 4949 \mu\text{m}^{-2}$.

Light-triggered aggregation of the 2- and 3- membered proteinosome mixtures

10 μL S proteinosomes were mixed with 10 μl of R1 or R2 proteinosomes in 2-membered communities or with 5 μL of R1 and 5 μl of R2 proteinosomes for 3-membered communities with 8 μl 3.5x DNA buffer (final buffer concentrations: 10 mM Tris pH 8, 12 mM MgCl_2 , 0.05% v/v Tween 20) in a $\mu\text{-Slide}$ 18 Well-Flat uncoated glass bottom dish (Ibidi GmbH, Martinsried, Germany). Afterward, the different samples were incubated for 90 min in the dark, under blue or red light (120 s ON, 360 s OFF) while shaking on a 2D shaker at 30 rpm. The proteinosomes were allowed to settle for 20-30 min before imaging.

For two membered communities, an area of $0.5 \times 0.5 \text{ mm}^2$ was imaged for each sample in the RhodB channel to visualize all proteinosomes. For analyzing the aggregation ratio, the images were converted into binary images and holes were filled using the “Fill holes” tool. Then, the area occupied by different proteinosomes, and their clusters (objects) was quantified using the “Analyze particle tool”. Objects larger than $2000 \mu\text{m}^2$ were considered as aggregates. Then proteinosomes within a cluster were separated by a 1 pixel line using the “Watershed” function. The number of proteinosomes in each sample was determined using the “Analyze Particle” function. Then the aggregation ratio was calculated from dividing the number proteinosomes in the cluster by the total number of proteinosomes in the sample.

For three membered communities, first the DSD reaction was carried out and at the end an area of $0.5 \times 0.5 \text{ mm}^2$ was imaged in the Rhod B (all proteinosomes), Atto425 (R2 proteinosomes), Alexa488 (S proteinosomes) and Cy5 (activated R proteinosomes) channels. The data was used to analyze both the aggregation ratio (see below) and the communication different populations.

DNA-Strand-Displacement (DSD) cascade

The proteinosome samples were allowed to aggregate under different illumination conditions as described above and were settled for 20-30 min. To start the DSD reaction, 2 μ L fuel strand (final concentration: 670 nM) and 2 μ L of the input strand (final concentration: 100 nM)^[8, 9] were added. The samples were imaged every 1 min for 70 min the Alexa488 (S activation) and Cy5 (R activation) channels using confocal microscopy. In 2-membered communities, the mean fluorescence in the Alex488 and Cy5 channels over time was analyzed for $n > 45$ randomly picked S and R proteinosomes, respectively and corrected for the background.

Image analysis in three membered communities

To analyze the aggregation behaviour of different pairs in the 3-membered community, first brightness and contrast in the different channels was adjusted (S+R1+R2=Rhod B, S=Alexa488, R2=Atto425, and activated R=Cy5) and different channels were used to compute the area occupied by different pairs (S+R1=Rhod B – Atto425, S+R2=Alexa488+Atto425, R1+R2=Rhod B – Alexa488). Subsequently, the images were converted into binary images and the clustered proteinosomes were detected using the “Analyze Particles” function, where only objects with an area $> 2000 \mu\text{m}^2$ were considered as aggregates. Then proteinosomes within a cluster were separated by a 1 pixel line using the “Watershed” function. The number of proteinosomes was determined using the “Analyze Particle” function. Finally, the aggregation ratio was calculated from dividing the number proteinosomes in the cluster by the total number of proteinosomes in the sample (Rhod B channel).

To analyze the communication within the three membered community, the images acquired in different channels were converted to binary images and interior of the proteinosomes was filled using the “Fill hole” function in ImageJ. A mask was created from the binary images using “Convert to mask” function and then proteinosomes within a cluster were separated by a 1 pixel line using the “Watershed” function. The number of proteinosomes in each population was determined using the “Analyze Particle” function. The activated R2 proteinosomes were defined as the overlap of the Atto425 and Cy5 channels, the activated R1 proteinosomes as the difference of the Cy5 from the Atto425 channels and the non-responders as the difference of the Rhod B channel from the Alexa488 and Cy5 channels. Finally, the population ratio was calculated by dividing the number of each population by the total number of proteinosomes in the sample.

Signal propagation in sender proteinosome

The F1 and F3 DNA strands were loaded into the sender proteinosome, and they were subsequently functionalized with iLID and PhyB proteins following the protocol described above. The DSD reaction was initiated, and the samples were imaged every 1 min for 60 min using the Cy5 channel (F3 signal strand) and Alexa488 (F1 strand) on confocal microscopy. The mean fluorescence intensity in the Cy5 channel across a horizontal line over time was analyzed and corrected for the background.

Measuring the diffusion of DNA signal through the proteinosome membrane

First, the control channels of microfluidic device were filled with MilliQ water and the pressure was set at 2 bar and the microfluidic tapping device was mounted on the stage of a confocal microscope (CLSM, Leica SP8). The pressure to the inlet channels was adjusted using adjustable pressure regulators (Flow-EZ, Fluigent). The buffer solution was connected to inlet 1. By closing all other inlet and outlet valves, and pressurizing the buffer channel at 1 bar, air bubbles were pushed out of the flow channels followed by thoroughly washing all the flow channels using the buffer solution. DNA-containing proteinosomes were loaded from the inlet 2 into the tapping array at a pressure of 10 mbar, Then the inlet 2 was closed and the proteinosomes were gently washed using ca. 5-15 mbar with buffer solution for 5-10 min to remove any unbound DNA. All experiments were performed at room temperature and the initial steady-state signals were recorded as the baseline values.

The DNA oligonucleotides were diluted in buffer solution with 2 mg/ml BSA to minimize DNA adsorption to tubing and loaded to inlet 3. Using 10 mbar pressure for 20 s, the DSD reactions were started and the pressure was then reduced to 3 mbar to maintain a slow flow (ca. 0.1 μ L/min) of DNA strand solution into the trapping chamber and thereby a constant input concentration in the extra extracellular medium. Estimation of proteinosome permeability and the rate constant was calculated using the mathematical model described before.^[8]

Data acquisition, and statistical analysis

All confocal microscopy images were acquired on a Leica DMi8 S laser scanning confocal microscope, equipped with 405, 488, 552 and 638 nm lasers and 20x/0.75 NA, 20x/0.75 IMM or 40x/1.10 W CS2 (field of view: 0.775x0.775 mm², slice thickness: 2 μ) objectives. All microscopy images were analyzed using the ImageJ 1.52b and LASX software. All values were reported as the mean \pm SEM, from three independent replicates. Significant differences between groups were analyzed using an unpaired t-test, *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, and ***p < 0.001.

	DNA sequence (5' \longrightarrow 3')	Number of bases	5' modification	3' modification
Input (A)	TAT TAC AGC GAA CGA ACG ACA CTA ATG CAC TAC TAC	36		
F1	GTA GTA GTG CAT TAG TGT CGT TCG TTC GCT GTA ATA	36	Alexa488	Biotin-TEG
F2	GCA TTA GTC TAT CAT GGT CGT TCG TTC GAC AGT TCC	36	Biotin-TEG	Cy5
Q1	CGA ACG AAC GAC CAT GAT AGA CTA ATG CAC TAC TAC	36		Iowa Black
Q2	GGA ACT GTC GAA CGA ACG TGA AAC CGA CCA TGA TAG	36	Iowa Black	phosphate
F3	CGA ACG AAC GAC CAT GAT AGA CTA ATG CAC TAC TAC	36		Cy5
Fuel	GGA ACT GTC GAA CGA ACG ACC ATG ATA G	28		phosphate

Table S1. DNA sequences used for DSD reactions in proteinosomes.

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Scheme S1. Synthesis of end-capped mercaptothiazoline-activated PNIPAM-co-NTA by RAFT polymerization. The end-capped mercaptothiazoline-activated PNIPAM was synthesized by reversible addition-fragmentation chain-transfer (RAFT) polymerization using a designed trithiol RAFT agent.^[6]

Figure S1. ¹H NMR (top) and ¹³C NMR (bottom) spectra of 2,20-(5-acrylamido-1-carboxypentylazanediy)ldiacetic acid (NTA-acrylate) (1). Spectra acquired in D₂O as the solvent and calibrated against residual protonated solvent (*).

Figure S2. ^1H NMR (top) and ^{13}C NMR (bottom) spectra of PNIPAM-co-NTA (2). Spectra acquired in CD_3OD as the solvent and calibrated against residual protonated solvent (*).

Figure S3. FT-IR spectrum of PNIPAM-co-NTA showing a carbonyl peak at 1739.53 cm⁻¹ that indicates successful incorporation of NTA in the polymeric chain.

Figure S4. MALDI spectrum of PNIPAM-co-NTA showing M_n 5760 g mol⁻¹, M_w 5800 g mol⁻¹, PDI 1.01.

Figure S5. Estimation of LCST for PNIPAM-co-NTA. The cloud point temperature (T_{cp}) was determined by measuring the transmittance between 500 and 600 nm for a polymer solution in water at a concentration of 1 mg mL^{-1} . The T_{cp} , taken as the 50% of the initial transmittance value, was determined to be $34 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Figure S6. Zeta potential (top) and hydrodynamic diameter (bottom) measurements of native BSA, cationized BSA and BSA/PNIPAM-co-NTA conjugate. Measurements carried out using 1 mg mL^{-1} solutions of protein or protein-polymer conjugate in 10 mM PBS buffer pH 7.0. Measurements repeated in triplicate and error bars are standard deviation of the mean. Passing from cationized BSA to protein-polymer conjugate it is evident a marked decrease in surface charge and increase in hydrodynamic diameter, confirming a successful conjugation of PNIPAM-co-NTA to cationized BSA.

Figure S7. FT-IR carbonyl region of BSA (light grey), PNIPAM-co-NTA (dark grey), and BSA/PNIPAM-co-NTA (red), showing successful conjugation of PNIPAM-co-NTA to cationized BSA.

Figure S8. MALDI spectrum of BSA/PNIPAM-co-NTA conjugate showing successful conjugation of at least 3 polymer chains to a single cationized BSA centre.

Figure S9. Estimation of LCST for PNIPAM-co-NTA (grey) and of BSA/PNIPAM-co-NTA conjugate (black). The cloud point temperature (T_{cp}) was determined by measuring the transmittance between 500 and 600 nm for a polymer or conjugate solution in water at a concentration of 1 mg mL^{-1} . The T_{cp} , taken as the 50% of the initial transmittance value, was determined to be $34.0 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $41.5 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for PNIPAM-co-NTA and of BSA/PNIPAM-co-NTA conjugate, respectively.

Figure S10. General procedure for preparation of proteinosomes. Cationized bovine serum albumin (BSA-NH₂) is synthesized via the previously reported procedure.^[6] Coupling of mercaptothiazoline-activated PNIPAM-co-NTA polymer chains with primary amine groups with cationized BSA-NH₂ gives protein-polymer conjugates (BSA-NH₂/PNIPAM-co-NTA). Carbodiimide-activated cationization of the aspartic and glutamic acid residues using the 1-6, hexandiamine enhanced the number of accessible amine groups available on the surface as well as the post-synthetic crosslinking. Micro-droplets were stabilized by a monolayer of closely packed protein-polymer conjugates and then crosslinked by using O,O'-Bis[2-(N-Succinimidylsuccinylamino)ethyl]polyethylene glycol (Mw 2,000; Sigma) at the water/oil droplet interface, and transferred into aqueous solution by removing the oil using a series of dialysis against water/ethanol mixtures.

Figure S11. Surface functionalization of proteinosomes with His-tagged proteins. A) Ni^{2+} -NTA groups on the surface of the proteinosomes bind to His-tagged proteins through the formation of the corresponding coordination complex after 20 min incubation. Confocal microscopy images in the i) Rhod B and ii) miCy channels for B) not loaded and C) Ni^{2+} loaded NTA-PNIPAM proteinosomes. miCy fluorescence only being visible in the Ni^{2+} loaded proteinosomes demonstrates the specific immobilization through the His-tag. The scale bars are 50 μm . Relation between solution His6-GFP concentration X and membrane bound His6-GFP density Γ for D) GUVs with 1 mol% DGS-NTA- Ni^{2+} and E) 1 mol% PNIPAM-co-NTA proteinosomes (see methods). The linear fit for GUVs is $\Gamma = (67 \pm 2) \times \mu\text{m}^{-2} \text{ nM}^{-1}$ ($R^2 = 9.99$) over the range of $0 < X \leq 23$ nM and for proteinosomes is $\Gamma = (109 \pm 8) \times \mu\text{m}^{-2} \text{ nM}^{-1}$ ($R^2 = 9.98$) over the range of $0 < X \leq 23$ nM. Error bars show the std. dev. of the mean ($n=3$).

Figure S12. Effect of protein-functionalization on proteinosome permeability and bimolecular rate constants. A) Fluorescence measurements (colored traces) and model fittings (black traces) of DSD reactions in proteinosomes functionalized with iLID or Nano protein vs. non-functionalized proteinosomes (control). Reactions were carried out with 100 nM of input (A) strand and to maintain a constant ssDNA concentration in the medium, the input strand solution was slowly flowed through the microfluidic chamber at a rate of approximately $0.1 \mu\text{l min}^{-1}$ throughout the experiment (see Methods). Concentrations of the activated DNA complex (F:A complex) were determined from time-dependent fluorescence measurements on individual protocells trapped within the microfluidic array device. B) Estimated permeability constants for the different proteinosomes. C) Estimated bimolecular rate constants for the DSD reactions inside the proteinosomes compared to the estimated rate constant for a reference DSD reaction under batch conditions as a control.^[8] Overall, the results demonstrate that the protein functionalization does not affect the DSD reaction and permeability of the proteinosomes significantly.

Figure S13. Contact sites between S and R1-type proteinosomes. A) 3D images of aggregated S and R1-type proteinosomes in the Rhod B channel after 90 min red light illumination. B) Aggregates of S and R1-type microcapsules after 90 min red light illumination and subsequently triggered DSD reaction. Alexa488 fluorescence in activated S proteinosomes is shown in green, Cy5 fluorescence of activated R proteinosomes is shown in red. Side view of C) Rhod B channel and D) Alexa488 and Cy5 channels across the white line are shown in (E) and (F), respectively. The images show large contact areas between the S and R1-type proteinosomes and membrane deformation due to the PhyB-PIF6 binding under red light.

Figure S14. Contact sites between S and R2-type proteinosomes. A) 3D images of aggregated S and R2-type proteinosomes in the Rhod B channel after 90 min blue light illumination. B) Aggregates of S and R2-type microcapsules after 90 min blue light illumination and subsequently triggered DSD reaction. Alexa 488 fluorescence in activated S proteinosomes is shown in green, Cy5 fluorescence of activated R proteinosomes is shown in blue. Side view of C) Rhod B channel and D) Alexa488 and Cy5 + Atto425 channels across the white line are shown in (E) and (F), respectively. The images show large contact areas between the S and R2-type proteinosomes and membrane deformation due to the iLID-Nano binding under blue light.

A

Figure S15. Size distribution of the proteinosomes. A) Confocal fluorescence images of proteinosomes in the Rhod B channel. The scale bar is 50 μm . B) Typical size distribution of proteinosomes. $n > 200$.

Figure S16. Encapsulation of the FITC-streptavidin in proteinosomes. A) Confocal fluorescence microscopy images of the proteinosomes in the FITC channel. The scale bar is 50 μm . B) Standardization curve for FITC-streptavidin at different concentrations. C) Calculated concentration of FITC-streptavidin encapsulated inside the proteinosomes. Error bar is mean \pm SD ($n = 3$).

Figure S17. DNA gate concentration in sender proteinosomes. A) Confocal fluorescence microscopy images of Alexa488 DNA strand at different concentration in a bulk solution and B) encapsulated inside the sender proteinosomes. The scale bar is 50 μm . B) Standardization curve for Alexa488 DNA gate at different concentrations. C) Calculated concentration of F1:A DNA gate encapsulated inside the proteinosomes. Error bar is mean \pm SD ($n = 4$).

Figure S18. Signal propagation from sender proteinosome. A) Upon addition of Input A strand the F3 strand with a Cy5 label is released from **S** and diffuses from the sender into the bulk over time. B) Confocal fluorescence microscopy images of the **S** proteinosome after initiating the DSD reaction. C) Fluorescent intensity of F3 strand in **S** plotted for different times as a function of distance across the yellow line. D) Confocal fluorescence microscopy images of **S** proteinosomes with different diameters. E) Fluorescent intensity of F3 strand in **S** plotted as a function of distance across the yellow line after 60 min of DSD reaction initiation. Dash line on the graph represents the periphery of the proteinosome. The fluorescence intensity of each protocell at 1 min intervals was obtained and the average of each distance was plotted for these time points (see methods). n=3

Figure S19. Activation of all receiver proteinosomes through the addition of external excess Q1 strand. A) In the dark, R1 and R2 proteinosomes are not in proximity of the S proteinosomes and the Q1 strand released from S proteinosomes can't reach the R proteinosomes. The subsequent external addition of excess Q1 strand activates Cy5 fluorescence both in the R1 and R2 populations. B) Confocal fluorescence microscopy images of 3-membered communities (S:R1:R2 ratio is 2:1:1) after initiating the DSD reaction. Excess Q1 strand (1.0 μ M) was added after 60 min. Alexa488 fluorescence in activated S proteinosomes is shown in green, Cy5 fluorescence of activated R proteinosomes is shown in red, Atto425 of R2 proteinosomes shown in blue in the merged image. The Cy5 fluorescence in R1 and R2 proteinosomes remained low even after activation of the S proteinosomes but increased both in R1 and R2 proteinosomes after the addition of excess Q1 strand, showing that they were functional. Scale bars are 50 μ m.